

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *VATERIA INDICA*

PART I. COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS OF THE FAT

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The fat from the seeds of *Vateria indica* contains 92.6% insoluble mixed fatty acids composed of 60.7% solid acids and 39.3% liquid acids. The composition of the fatty acids is found to be 0.2% lower acid, 0.7% myristic acid, 13% palmitic acid, 45.1% stearic acid, 0.4% arachidic acid, 42.5% oleic acid and 0.1% linoleic acid. The non-saponifiable matter is mainly composed of sitosterol and a trace of another sterol whose bromoacetate melts at 120-23° to a dark coloured liquid. Further, the fat on steam-distillation yields 0.05% of a terpenoid oil having an iodine value of 148.

The fat known as Malabar-tallow is obtained from the seeds of *Vateria indica* (N. O. Deptero-carpacæ, Vernacular, *Safed Damar*), a large ever-green tree found in Mysore, South Canara, Malabar and Travancure. The seeds yield on boiling with water 20% of a solid greenish-white fat with a pleasant flavour and agreeable taste, which is mainly used for edible purposes in South Kanara. This fat was used to be exported to Europe some years ago from Mangalore for uses as chocolate fat. Menon ("Manufacture of Soap in India") reports that this fat can replace tallow in the preparation of household and good toilet soaps. Further it has been shown to be suitable for yarn sizing and compares well with the high-class hydrogenated fats and animal tallows. A sample of the fat was obtained through the courtesy of the Forest Utilization Officer, Madras.

The present work is undertaken to investigate thoroughly the fatty acid composition of the fat since conflicting statements are made by the previous authors regarding the identifications of the various acids present (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology of Oils and Fats", Vol. II, p. 590; Forest Research Reports in India, 1930-31, p. 224; 1931-32, p. 72; Jones, Hilditch and Saletoore, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 4681; Puntambekar and Krishna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 205), and also to find out the glyceride structure of the fat. Chemical and physical constants of the fat are given in Table I along with those observed by others.

TABLE I

	Present workers.	Forest Research Reports, India.	Jones & co-workers.	Puntambekar & Krishna.
M. p.	36-37°	—	—	40°
d ₄ ²⁰	0.8989	—	—	at 25°, 0.9120
Ref. index*	1.4578 at 40°	1.4556 at 25°	—	at 25°, 1.4556
Sap. value	191.1	175	184.8	190.4
I. value	36.72 (Wij'a)	40.75	42.8	40.0 (Hanna)
Non. sap.	0.588%	—	—	0.8%
Hebner value	92.6	—	—	97.6
Acid value	2.88	1.4	8.8	1.4

* With Butyro-refractometer.

705 G. of the fat were saponified with strong alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide and the fatty acids were separated by splitting the soap. The chemical and physical properties of these insoluble acids and those of the liquid and solid acids separated by the lead salt-alcohol method (Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) with slight modifications are given below along with the recordings of others.

TABLE II

Mixed acids	Present workers	Forest Research Reports.	Jones & co-workers.	Puntaumbekar & Krishna.
Sap. equiv.	269.4	286	—	286
I. value	38.8	38.6	—	38.6
Sol. Pt.	55.9*	—	—	—
M. p.	55.6*	—	—	—
Sol. acids(%)	60.7 < ^{S.R.} 280.7 I.V. 7.07	53	55.6	61
Liq. acids(%)	39.3 < ^{S.R.} 280.0 I.V. 87.9	47	44.4	39

Ether soluble portion of the lead salts are mixed up with the alcohol solubles.

The fatty acids were converted into methyl esters and the esters were subjected to fractional distillation under reduced pressure of 2 mm.

TABLE III

Fractionation of esters of liquid acids

Esters, 132.5 g.; S.E., 293.6; I.V., 83.8.

Fr. No.	Temp. of fraction.	Wt. of fraction.	S.E.	I.V.	Identifications.
1	82-139°	3.5 g.	259.6	53.2	Lower acid (C ₁₈), myristic, palmitic & oleic.
2	147-149°	6.5	284.6	68.1	Myristic, palmitic and oleic.
3	149-151°	16.2	294.0	80.0	Palmitic & oleic.
4	151-158°	26.0	294.8	82.8	Palmitic & oleic
5	158°	7.4	295.2	83.8	Palmitic, oleic & linoleic.
6	159-175	13.4	295.5	84.5	Palmitic, oleic & linoleic.
7	175°	29.5	295.8	85.9	Oleic & linoleic
8	Residue	30.0	295.7*	85.4	Oleic, linoleic & non-sap.

TABLE IV

Fractionation of esters of solid acids

Esters, 144.9 g.; S.E., 294.6; I.V., 6.91.

Fr. No.	Temp. of fraction.	Wt. of fraction.	S.E.	I.V.	Identifications.
1	120-141°	2.8 g.	265.6	9.8	Myristic, palmitic & oleic.
2	142-149°	5.2	285.8	6.1	Palmitic, stearic and oleic.
3	149-152°	45.9	289.4	5.6	"
4	152-154°	21.2	289.5	5.8	"
5	154-163°	37.4	293.6	6.2	"
6	163-170°	7.5	296.3	6.2	"
7	170-172°	7.4	296.4	6.6	"
8	Residue	17.5	298.7	12.6	Oleic, stearic & arachidic.

* Corrected value.

Fraction No. 1 of the liquid esters gave a terpenoid oil, I.V. about 148. All the above identifications were carried out by usual methods of crystallisations and analysis for the chemical characteristics and finding the mixed melting points with authentic samples. Oleic acid was identified by oxidation with alkaline permanganate according to Lapworth and Mottram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628) when dihydroxystearic acid, m.p. 130°, without any other secondary product, was obtained. Further, the position of ethylinic linkage was determined by disruptive oxidation of the methyl oleate with potassium permanganate in acetone medium (Armstrong and Hilditch, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 447) when azelaic and nonoic acids were obtained showing that the acid is $\Delta^{9,10}$ -oleic acid. *iso*Oleic acid was found to be absent.

Linoleic acid was identified by separating oleic and linoleic acids partially by lithium salt formation and crystalliation from alcohol and then oxidising with alkaline permanganate in cold, when pure tetrahydroxystearic acid, m.p. 171°, was obtained. Oleic acid and linoleic acids were further identified by bromination by the method of Eibner and Mugantballer and then separating the tetrabromide, m.p. 114°, from petroleum ether almost quantitatively.

From the above identifications the acids are calculated on percentage basis and given below along with the recorded results of previous workers.

TABLE V

	Present workers.			Forest Research reports.	Jones & co-workers.	Pantambekar & Krishna.
	Sol. acid % (60.7%)	Liq. acid % (39.3%)	Total fatty acid (%)			
Lower						
acids (C ₁₈)	—	0.4	0.2	—	—	—
Myristic	9.3	1.4	0.7	—	—	Inferred (not isolated)
Palmitic	20.0	2.1	13.0	6	10.2	—
Stearic	71.1	—	43.1	45	38.9	59
Arachidic	0.7	—	0.4	2	3.1	Lignoceric.
Oleic	7.9	95.2	42.5	47	47.8	39
						(Oleic & <i>iso</i> oleic)
Linoleic	—	0.2	0.1	—	—	—

Non-saponifiable Matter.—The non-saponifiable matter obtained from the last fraction of the liquid esters was crystallised from methyl alcohol and acetone mixture (5:1) when balls of crystals in the form of plates separated which melted at 129-30° and gave all the colour reactions of sterols. The acetate gave crystals similar to the sterol itself melting at 127-29° on bromination of the acetates by the method of Windaus and Hauth (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4378) no precipitate came down showing the absence of stigma and brassica sterols. However, on concentrating the ether solution, a crystalline substance separated. This on crystallisation from chloroform-alcohol mixture (1:1) melted at 120-22° into a dark coloured liquid.

Steam-distillation of the Fat.—100 G. of the raw fat were steam-distilled and 5 litres of distillate were collected and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with dilute alkali to remove the free fatty acid that came with the distillate and on evaporation yielded a small quantity (0.05 g.) of essential oil having I.V. 148. This resembled the terpenoid oil obtained from the first fraction of the liquid esters.

C O N C L U S I O N

The fatty acids of *Vateria indica* consist of myristic (0.7%), palmitic (13%), stearic (43.1%), oleic (42.5%), arachidic (0.4%) and linoleic (0.1%) acids.

Puntambekar and Krishna (*loc. cit.*), mentioned the presence of *isoleic* acid but they did not carry either oxidation methods or reversion methods for confirmation. Repeated efforts by the present authors did not give any positive indication of its presence. From the last fraction of solid esters pure arachidic acid was isolated and identified. But no lignoceric acid could be detected.

Failure of Jones to detect the presence of myristic and linoleic acids may be attributed to the small quantity of fat at her disposal for carrying out the work and the small percentage of acids in the fat.

Presence of a new sterol whose bromo-acetate melted to a dark coloured liquid at 120-22° was indicated. Fine smelling essential oil (0.05%) on fat having iodine value of about 148 was isolated. Further work on the characterisation of the above is in progress.

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